

Supplementary Table S1. Depth range for each stromboid family, with relevant literature or museum registration number of a specimen collected from that depth. Also given is the most detailed literature reference for normal locomotion and predator avoidance behaviour. Treatment of depth uncertainty associated with trawl data followed Bouchet et al. (2008); see Methods for detailed description. Abbreviations: MNHN, Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle; UF, Florida Museum of Natural History; NA, not applicable (unknown). Asterisk (*) mark specimens examined by the authors.

Family	Depth range (m)	Reference (minimum depth)	Reference (maximum depth)	Normal locomotion	Withdrawal into shell	Escape behaviour
Aporrhaidae	6–1,000	Wieneke et al. (2022) coll. Ulrich Weineke UW 1405	Wieneke et al. (2022) coll. Eddy Wilmet	Leaping (Perron 1978)	NA	Slow escape behaviour (Perron 1978)
Rostellariidae	1–575	UF 521337*	MNHN-IM-2013-64503*	Leaping (Adams 1848)	NA	NA
Seraphsidae	0–50	MNHN-IM-2019-1737*	MNHN-IM-2012-19470	Leaping or burrowing forwards (Adams 1848; Jung and Abbott 1967)	Withdrawal (Adams 1848)	Rapid, directional escape behaviour (Savazzi 1991)
Strombidae	0–780	MNHN-IM-2013-47450	MNHN-IM-2007-36711*	Leaping (Adams, 1848; Berg 1975)	Withdrawal (Berg 1975)	Rapid, directional escape behaviour (Kohn and Waters 1966; Berg 1975)

Struthiolariidae	0–1,150	Hayward et al. (1981, 1999)	Auckland Museum (via OBIS) MA138730	Leaping (Morton 1951)	Withdrawal (Crump 1968)	Non-directional flips (Crump 1968)
Xenophoridae	0–1,500	Tunnell (2010)	UF 111856	Leaping (Berg 1975)	Withdrawal (Berg 1975)	No escape response (Berg 1975)

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